

SYSTEM OF INDICATORS REPRESENTING COMPETITIVENESS AND EFFICIENCY IN SERVICE ENTERPRISES AND THEIR ANALYSIS

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Annotation. In this article, the author carried out research and analysis of the system of indicators representing competitiveness and efficiency in service enterprises and developed suggestions and recommendations within the scope of the topic.

Key words: service, competition, competitiveness, efficiency, the state, the economy, the model, marketing, innovation, the system.

Introduction. Today, large-scale measures are being taken to develop the service sector in our country. Non-governmental organizations, in particular, private business entities, are also involved in this on a large scale. As a result, the number of competitors increased and the transition to a new market system requiring pure competition. The formation of a competitive environment is primarily related to the year-by-year increase in the number of service enterprises. The existence of enterprises with different forms of ownership was the impetus for the creation of a competitive environment among service enterprises in Uzbekistan.

Analysis of the literature on the subject. Some theoretical, methodological and practical aspects of increasing the competitiveness and efficiency of service enterprises are discussed by foreign scientists such as F.Kotler, M.Porter, G.L.Azoyev, A.P.Chelenkov, V.V.Balakshin, and Uzbek scientists B.A.Abdukarimov. , M.Q.Pardayev, K.J.Mirzayev, K.B.Urazov, I.Ivatov, O.M.Pardayev and Sh.A.Sultanov are working.

In these studies, when the problems of improving the competitiveness and efficiency of service enterprises are studied, not enough attention is paid to the

specific new directions of modern service enterprises. It is these aspects of the issue that determine the relevance of the topic of the article.

In the generally recognized methods of assessing competitiveness, "product quality improvement" is seen as the main factor[1], but the experiences of schools formed in its analysis differ. For example, in the Japanese model, "upgrading the quality system" is considered as the main factor, while the French use "marketing activities" as the main factor, while the American methods use more "market leadership" or "market share assessment" methods[2] . In the countries of the European Union, the most reliable indicator of competitiveness is the assessment of the ability of enterprises to maintain productivity and efficiency for a long time [3].

According to the theory of effective competition, which is based on a full assessment of the competitiveness of a service enterprise, the level of competitiveness of an enterprise with a well-organized product production, sales and financial management system is considered high [4]. The methodology is based on four groups of indicators or criteria of competitiveness determined by the method of step-by-step comparison of experts: the efficiency determining the production activity of the enterprise, the efficiency determining the financial situation of the enterprise, the efficiency of organizing the sale and promotion of the goods in the market, and the competitiveness of the goods. There are only two main functions of an enterprise: marketing and innovation [5]. It is appropriate to consider innovative activity as the main factor of competitiveness. Professor M.Q. Pardayev justified that "a number of indicators can be used to express the competitiveness of economic entities [6].

Analysis and results. the expansion of the service sector in our republic, the training of personnel with scientific potential, the increasing role of modern industries, the development of service enterprises, and the provision of a competitive environment in the service market depend more on the level of

resource potential.

Table 1

The main socio-economic indicators of the development of Samarkand region

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T/r	Indicators	Unit of measure	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1.	GDP	billion soums	32863,7	39050,5	43386,6	53749,9	62440,3
		Compared to last year, %	100,7	105,6	102,4	108,8	105,8
2.	Gross value added	billion soums	30659,5	36479,7	42478,3	52640,7	60866,2
		Compared to last year, %	101,3	104,0	102,4	108,8	105,7
3.	Net taxes on products	billion soums	574,0	1114,2	908,3	1 109,2	1574,1
		Compared to last year, %	109,0	108,4	107,8	108,8	109,7
4.	Industrial output (including construction)	billion soums	6216,7	7206,0	8 654,9	10523,1	13 474,5
		Compared to last year, %	114,1	110,5	107,1	112,9	109,3
5.	Agricultural products	billion soums	15 295,1	16 862,4	19 225,8	22672,3	24 652,2
		Compared to last year, %	94,4	102,9	102,7	103,3	103,6
6.	Total Services, from which:	billion soums	10 595,9	13 583,3	14 234,2	18589,0	22 739,5

¹ Author's development: Compiled based on the information of the State Statistics Department of Samarkand region.

		Compared to last year, %	103,1	105,9	97,4	112,6	106,3
10.	Shopping, accommodation and dining services	billion soums	1966,3	2411,1	2680,8	3350,6	4190,8
		Compared to last year, %	103,1	106,9	100,3	112,1	111,0
11.	Transportation and storage, information and communication services	billion soums	2087,2	2329,3	2482,1	3299,6	3876,6
		Compared to last year, %	105,9	104,5	98,3	122,8	110,9
12.	Other services	billion soums	6542,4	8842,8	9071,3	11938,9	14672,1
		Compared to last year, %	102,1	106,1	96,4	110,0	103,7

Currently, more than 316,000 enterprises and organizations are operating in the territory of the republic. Of these, 209,500 enterprises and organizations operate in the service sector. The share of enterprises and organizations operating in the field of services in the total number of enterprises and organizations is 66.1%. In January-October 2023, 176,819 legal entities engaged in service activities paid more than 17.9 trillion soums in taxes. More than 3.5 trillion soums, i.e. 20%, are accounted for by 20 enterprises. Their total turnover was 33.8 trillion soums, and the amount of tax benefits they used was 2.3 trillion soums.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, increasing the competitiveness of service enterprises with the status of a legal entity among the economic entities operating at the stage of development of the current service enterprises is becoming a very urgent issue.

The process of researching the activities of competing service enterprises

should be carried out in three stages:

- Determining the number of existing competing service enterprises;
- Analysis of competitive indicators of competing service enterprises;
- Identifying strengths and weaknesses of competitive service enterprises.

The organization and improvement of the activity of the service enterprises is very important today, and it is necessary to develop methods of analysis that continuously study the activity of each service enterprise.

The information given above is used to analyze the competitiveness of service enterprises today, to draw appropriate conclusions based on the results of the analysis and to study the issues of ensuring competitiveness, first of all, to develop a system of indicators representing competitiveness and ways to determine them. showing that it is one of the most urgent issues.

To date, scientists have conducted a number of scientific studies on the evaluation of the competitiveness of service enterprises, but there are different views on the development of a specific system of indicators for the evaluation of the competitiveness of the enterprise. In economic literature, the methods of assessing the competitiveness of service enterprises based on the products (work, services) produced, the efficiency of the activity and the level of marketing activities are widely used in practice.

The main characteristics of the Japanese model are based on the study of the degree of compliance of the product with consumer demand, while the French model examines the degree of compliance of the production with the marketing activities of the enterprise. The main feature of the American model in assessing competitiveness is the company's position in the market and its market opportunities.

Based on the methods of evaluating the competitiveness of the enterprise proposed above, we found it appropriate to develop criteria and indicators that represent the competitiveness of service enterprises.

One of the important stages in the analysis of the activity of service enterprises

is to express each category in appropriate indicators. This, in turn, requires the development of indicators representing competitiveness. But this issue

This situation makes the development of a system of indicators related to competitiveness in service enterprises an objective necessity today. However, in the economic literature studied during the research, the quantitative indicators that evaluate the competitiveness of the activities of trading entities and provide a basis for drawing appropriate conclusions after analysis have not been studied.

Therefore, we present our views on the criteria and indicators of the competitiveness of service enterprises.

There are many views on the criteria of competitiveness in the economic literature. Russian scientists use the term "Criteria" more often.

The word "criterion" is derived from the Greek word "kriterzin", which means a sign of evaluating something, defining or classifying something, measuring it [7]. The Uzbek meaning of the term "criterion" means "criterion".

The criterion should be understood as a measure of the qualitative content of events, processes, situations, etc., as a sign of an opinion about them. Its numerical measurements are reflected in indicators.

This criterion is considered a target indicator, and with the help of this indicator, it is possible to determine whether the enterprise has achieved a certain level of competitiveness.

The criterion should be that the enterprise has achieved its ultimate goal of competitiveness.

The criteria describing the competitiveness of the service enterprise must meet the following requirements;

- 1) Determination of the final result of the efficiency of the economic activity of the service enterprise;
- 2) Determining the level of expenses incurred by the service enterprise in order to achieve its goals;

3) to be universal for comparison (comparison) with criteria of other service enterprises.

We recommend evaluating the competitiveness of the service enterprise using the following criteria (Table 2).

Table 2

Criteria and indicators of service enterprise competitiveness²

Competitive criteria	Indicators of competitiveness
Criteria for assessing the condition of the material and technical base of the service enterprise	Coefficient of change of basic funds Coefficient of change of working capital Coefficient of change of service area
Criteria for evaluating the financial status of a service enterprise	Coefficient of change in the volume of service turnover Coefficient of change of net profit Solvency ratio
Criteria for evaluating the performance of service enterprise employees	The coefficient of change of highly educated employees Employee dissatisfaction Labor productivity coefficient
Criteria for evaluating the quality of customer service in a service company	Coefficient of customer satisfaction with services (feedback on services). Coefficient of change in the number of regular customers Coefficient of change of population using services

² Author development

The criteria of competitiveness of the service enterprise mentioned above are closely related to each other. A change in one of the indicators leads to a change in the rest of the indicators.

Professor M.Q. Pardayev "proved that the following system of indicators can be used to express the competitiveness of economic entities".

1. The share of the product of the service enterprise in the same products in the market (Kmbu);

2. Product share (Kmu) of the same enterprise compared to the share of the enterprise's product (ECmu) of the strongest competitor in the market;

3. The growth rate of the volume of sales of competitive products (Rmo's);

4. The amount of the price of the product of the service enterprise in the coefficient compared to the price of such product in the market (Kbah);

5. Certification level of the product of the service enterprise (Xer);

6. The ratio of profit from product advertising in a service enterprise to advertising costs (Crack);

7. Profitability level of competitive goods of the service enterprise (Rrb);

8. General rate of return (R) in a service enterprise;

9. The current level of liquidity of the balance sheet of the service enterprise (Lj);

10. Generalized indicator (Mruk) representing the competitiveness of the service enterprise's product.

There are views of other scientists on this issue, but most of them are mainly focused on the issue of competitiveness of production and industrial [8] enterprises. Therefore, without dwelling on the views and opinions of other scientists on these issues, we would like to cite the indicators that represent the competitiveness of the service enterprises that are the object of our research. We recommend dividing such a system of indicators into four groups:

1. Indicators representing the competitiveness of the material and technical base of the service enterprise (Mtb);
2. Indicators representing the competitiveness of the financial situation of the service enterprise (Mh);
3. Competitiveness indicators related to the activity of employees of the service enterprise (Mh);
4. Competitiveness indicators for the quality of customer service (Xks).

Indicators representing the competitiveness of the service enterprise can be represented by chart 1.

Figure 1. Indicators of service enterprise competitiveness

Currently, all indicators are determined on the basis of practical data, based on the purpose, we summarize the indicators that express the competitiveness of service enterprises, the formula for calculating indicators and the explanations of the formulas, and the indicators that express the competitiveness of service enterprises we divided into 4 groups according to economic content (Table 2). For

this, we used the aggregation method of determining complex indicators. Using this method, the following formula can be used to determine the complex indicator of the competitiveness of the service enterprise (Skrk):

Table 2

The system of indicators representing the competitiveness of the service enterprise and ways of determining them³

T/r	Indicator name	Formula	Explanation
I. Xizmat ko'rsatish korxonasining moddiy-texnika bazasi bo'yicha (Mtb)			
1.1.	The coefficient of renewal of the main funds (Af.ya _k)	$\text{Af.ya}_k = \frac{\text{YaAf}_{hy}}{\text{Af}_{yo}}$	YaAf_{hy} – the amount in the reporting year of the fixed funds included in the new work; Af_{yo} - the initial amount of the main funds at the end of the year.
1.2.	Coefficient of change of working capital (Ay.m _k)	$\text{Ay.m}_k = \frac{\text{Ay.m}_{hy}}{\text{Ay.m}_{oy}}$	Ay.m_{hy} – the amount of working capital in the reporting year; Ay.m_{oy} - the amount of working capital in the previous year.
1.3.	Coefficient of change of service area (Smo'k)	$\text{Smo}'_k = \frac{\text{Sm}_{hy}}{\text{Sm}_{oy}}$	Sm_{hy} - the size of the service area in the reporting year; Sm_{oy} - the size of the service area in the last year.
II. On the financial status of the service enterprise (Mh)			
2.1.	The coefficient of change of the turnover volume (TA _k)	$\text{TA}_k = \frac{\text{TA}_{hy}}{\text{TA}_{oy}}$	TA_{hy} – the amount of turnover in the reporting year; TA_{oy} - the amount of turnover of the last year.

³ These indicators have been improved by the author.

2.2.	Coefficient of change of net profit (Sf_k)	$Sf_k = \frac{Sf_{hy}}{Sf_{o'y}}$	Sf_{hy} – the amount of net profit in the reporting year; $Sf_{o'y}$ - the amount of net profit for the previous year
2.3.	The coefficient of variation of the costs of marketing activities (Mfx_k)	$Mfx_k = \frac{Mfh_{hy}}{Mfh_{o'y}}$	Mfx_{hy} – the amount of marketing activity expenses in the reporting year; $Mfx_{o'y}$ – last year's sum of marketing expenses.
III. According to the activity (professional level) of the employees of the service enterprise (Xf)			
3.1.	The coefficient of change of the number of highly educated service workers (Oxs_k)	$Oxs_k = \frac{Oxs_{hy}}{Oxs_{o'y}}$	Oxs_{hy} – the number of sales employees with higher education in the reporting year; $Oxs_{o'y}$ - the number of sales employees with higher education last year.
3.2.	Coefficient of change in the number of qualified sales personnel (Msx_k)	$Msx_k = \frac{Msx_{hy}}{Msx_{o'y}}$	Msx_{hy} – the number of qualified sales personnel in the reporting year; $Msx_{o'y}$ - the number of qualified sales personnel in the past year.
3.3.	The coefficient of change of labor productivity of sales staff ($Musx_k$)	$Musx_k = \frac{Musx_{hy}}{Musx_{o'y}}$	$Musx_{hy}$ – indicator of labor productivity in the reporting year; $Musx_{o'y}$ – last year's indicator of labor productivity.
IV. On the quality of customer service (Xks)			

4.1.	Coefficient of change of customer satisfaction with services (Xxq_k)	$\mathbf{Xxq}_k = \frac{Xqxs_{hy}}{Xqxs_{o'y}}$	Xqxs_{hy} – number of customers satisfied with services in the reporting year; Xqxs_{o'y} - the number of customers satisfied with services in the last year.
4.2.	The coefficient of renewal of the assortment of goods (Tasya_k)	$\mathbf{Tasya}_k = \frac{Tas_{hy}}{Tas_{o'y}}$	Tas_{hy} – number of assortment of goods in the reporting year; Tas_{o'y} – number of assortment of goods last year.
4.3.	Coefficient of change of population using services (Xfas_k)	$\mathbf{Xfas}_k = \frac{Xfas_{hy}}{Xfas_{o'y}}$	Xfas_{hy} – the number of people who used the services in the reporting year; Xfas_{o'y} – the number of people who benefited from services last year.

$$\mathbf{Skrk} = \sum_{i=1}^n xi \quad (1)$$

In this: $\sum_{i=1}^n$ – plus sign; i – ordinal number of indicators to be aggregated; n - the total number of aggregated indicators; $xi - i$ – the amount of the indicator.

If we apply this formula, it is possible to sum up the coefficients of indicators of 4 groups and determine the overall indicator.

$$\mathbf{Skrk} = \sum_{i=1}^n xi = \sum_{i=1}^3 \mathbf{Mtb} + \sum_{i=1}^3 \mathbf{Mh} + \sum_{i=1}^3 \mathbf{Xf} + \sum_{i=1}^3 \mathbf{Xks} \quad (2)$$

I. According to the material technical base (MTB), II. Financial status of the service enterprise (MH) and III. If almost all the information for determining the indicators of the employees' activity (professional level) is reflected in the financial and other reports IV. Indicators of the quality of customer service (QS)

in the service enterprise are determined on the basis of questionnaires conducted with customers.

The use of the proposed comprehensive index of competitiveness assessment allows to achieve positive results in the activity of service enterprises. In particular, this methodology makes it possible to increase economic efficiency due to strengthening competitiveness.

Conclusion. In short, the theoretical study of ensuring the competitiveness of service enterprises and increasing their economic efficiency shows that, first of all, this issue has not been considered sufficiently from the point of view of market relations and the specific development of our country. Secondly, correspondingly, this issue is still poorly covered by the scientists of our country in the economic literature. Thirdly, due to the fact that many problems of ensuring the competitiveness and increasing the efficiency of service enterprises are still waiting for their solution, it requires a lot of scientific research aimed at studying them.

References

1. Maurice Stucke, “Is competition Always Good” Journal of Antitrust Enforcement 4 n.17 (forthcoming 2013).
2. Смолейчук И.М. Организационно-экономические основы повышения конкурентоспособности легкой промышленности. Диссертация доктора экономических наук. – Владивосток, 2003. С-105.
3. Birhan Getaneh. Competitiveness Analysis of Ethiopian Furniture Industry. Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. 2014. P11.
4. Boltabaev M.R. O‘zbekistonda to‘qimachilik mahsulotlari eksportini rivojlantirishning marketing strategiyalari. 08.00.13 – “Marketing ixtisosligi” bo‘yicha i.f.d. ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan dissertatsiya, Toshket-2005.
5. Drucker, P.F. Management: tasks, responsibilities, practices, Transaction Publishers, New Brunswick, N.J.; London. 2007.

6. Pardaev M.Q., Isroilov J.I. Xususiy korxonalar faoliyati tahlilining nazariy va metodologik muammolari. Monografiya. – T.: “Fan va texnologiya”, 2007.- 107-109 betlar.

7. Словарь иностранных слов. М.: Русский язык. 1985. С. 262.

8. Hakimov Z.A. Yengil sanoat korxonalari raqobatbardoshligini oshirish omillari. Monografiya. – T.: “Iqtisod-Moliya”, 2016.